

An Analysis of Security Concerns in Transitioning Battery Management Systems from First to Second Life

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ABSTRACT

Lithium-ion batteries are becoming essential vehicle components with the ongoing shift to electric vehicles. Battery management systems manage these batteries. Typically, battery management systems used to be placed deep within the vehicle architecture, away from external interfaces. However, with increasing connectivity to backend systems, e.g., to improve monitoring battery properties and optimize charging, battery management systems have moved closer to the attack surface, increasing security risks. Also, batteries will soon be reused in so-called second life applications, e.g., as an energy storage system in a private home. While conventional methods involve removing the battery and reusing it with a new battery management system, modern methods retain the original system. Though security controls exist for first and second life applications, there is a lack of research on the transition phase. This paper analyzes the phase of transferring the battery management system from the first to the second life of particular relevance for security, privacy, and intellectual property. We try to close this research gap by analyzing the security aspects of a battery management system life cycle and its altering system environment. We are defining the transition phase, identifying necessary activities, and providing cybersecurity needs for the transitioning of battery management systems from first to second life.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy → Embedded systems security; Domain-specific security and privacy architectures.

KEYWORDS

battery management system, BMS, second life batteries, cybersecurity, security control, transition

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1 INTRODUCTION

The sales volume of electric vehicles (EVs) and thus the production and use of high-voltage batteries is rising significantly due to the global aim of reducing greenhouse gases [11]. Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) require the use of a hardware-software-compound, known as battery management system (BMS), as supervisor to ensure the battery's safe operation. The BMS has functionalities to communicate with the charging station, enhance the charging profile, exchange authentication data, and send status information, e.g., to the in-vehicle infotainment (IVI). The upcoming Battery Pass requirement [7] aims to provide battery-related data for owners, original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), recyclers, and auditing institutions such as the European Union (EU). In addition to meeting this requirement, connectivity will be enhanced, e.g., to allow functional upgrades for the BMS or to integrate it into smart home applications. As a result of these changes, the connections of the BMS to the outside world are becoming increasingly important and widespread. Incorporating these features creates a more user-friendly, environmentally conscious, and energy-efficient experience for different stakeholders. At the same time, however, the surface for attacks on confidentiality, integrity, and availability increases. While the nature of the attacks and their general consequences are consistent with those targeting other cyber physical systems (CPSs), these attacks specifically differ in that they focus on the critical role of the battery in ensuring vehicle functionality, occupant safety, and preserving resale value. Therefore, the integration of cybersecurity controls is a mandatory task in the development and operation of BMS for LIBs.

Most of the parts and components installed in a vehicle will be connected to the vehicle up to their end of life (EOL). Their service life ends when the vehicle is decommissioned or when the component becomes faulty and gets replaced. However, this statement is not valid for batteries: the United States Advanced Battery Consortium [28] states that an EV battery can no longer be used for a vehicle if its capacity degrades to 80% of its original amount. However, the battery may still be suitable for other usage scenarios than in the automotive domain, e.g., as storage for photovoltaic (PV) systems or as emergency energy supply in hospitals [24]. As batteries are mainly made from natural materials, second life applications are mandatory from a climate protection perspective, fostering the circular economy concept. Conventional methods involve disassembling the battery and then reassembling it with a new BMS for its second life application. Modern methods use the original BMS from the first life to be reconfigured and reuse the battery in its current state to facilitate the reuse of batteries. The new EU Battery

Regulation also requires opportunities to reuse BMS [7]. Hence, the life cycle of a battery and its associated BMS does not end with the end of the vehicle but can continue in a different environment.

To address these aspects, in this paper, we make the following contributions to extend the state of the art:

- Literature survey on the cybersecurity life cycle of a BMS
- Analysis of the security aspect in a BMS life cycle
- Definition of the transition between first and second life of a BMS with a special focus on cybersecurity aspects
- Cybersecurity needs for the transition phase

These contributions can be an entry point for a succeeding threat analysis and risk assessment (TARA) as described in the ISO/SAE 21434 [15]. The remaining paper is structured as follows: background information on BMS is introduced in Section 2. Related works on system environment and battery life cycle are given in Section 3. In Section 4, the system environment in a first and second life is introduced. Section 5 presents life cycle stages relevant to the BMS and describes the cybersecurity activities in each stage. Finally, the transition phase is defined, and cybersecurity needs are derived (Section 6). The findings and results and an overview of future activities are summarized in Section 7.

2 AUTOMOTIVE BMS

Models of BMS are already defined within many research works [1, 16–19, 25, 29]. Therefore, we are summarizing the most essential aspects of BMS as shown by these authors to give generalized background information on the state of the art of a BMS. These aspects are also consistent with the data sheets of current commercial BMS [12, 20].

2.1 General

The battery of an EV consists inevitably of cells and a corresponding BMS: it is of great importance to monitor and control the physical limits of a LIB. Therefore, a system of software and hardware that takes over these tasks is mandatory. Cells and BMS are built into one unit divided into several sub-parts and comprise several functions and interfaces (Figure 1). Current architectures follow a master-slave concept where slave modules monitor only one group of cells. Future designs use a cell-to-pack (C2P) structure connecting all cells to one master BMS [29].

2.2 Functions

The functionalities of a BMS can be split into internal and external functions and functions that ensure the safety of the BMS and, thus, of the vehicle and its occupants.

2.2.1 Internal. Internal functions flow between the BMS and the cells, modules, or packs. These functions are mandatory for every BMS as they ensure the system’s safety. The main function of a BMS is to monitor and control the system parameters voltage, current, and temperature. The BMS also calculates state of charge (SoC), state of health (SoH), and state of energy (SoE). Statuses are relevant for controlling vehicle performance and indicating them to the user. An internal balancing function comprises methods to reduce the cell’s spread in each individual SoC [22].

Figure 1: BMS and Battery.

2.2.2 External. External functions add additional and mainly optional features to a BMS and its environment. External communication occurs as part of the communication with the charging station to transmit charging requests. Provisioning of SoC or SoH, for example, to the IVI and communication with other electronic control units (ECUs), e.g., the vehicle control unit (VCU) are also examples of external communication. Future trends tend to perform advanced and AI-based calculations in a cloud-based environment. The Battery Pass, which is mandatory for future batteries, will also store static and dynamic battery data on remote servers [7]. Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) offers the opportunity to use the energy stored in the vehicle’s battery in the grid to balance consumption peaks or for powering buildings (vehicle-to-building (V2B)). Extensive communication between external parties and the internal BMS is necessary to enable these future functions.

2.2.3 Safety Functions. The main functionality of a BMS is to ensure the battery’s and, therefore, the vehicle’s and the occupant’s safety. The BMS contains functions to monitor the battery pack’s voltage, current, and temperature and intervenes if these values are outside their safe boundaries. Otherwise, an uncontrolled temperature rise can cause thermal runaway, posing a danger to passengers and the environment.

It is reasonable to think about functions integrated into a BMS on demand so that the functionalities of the BMS are expanded over time [10].

2.3 Interfaces

The described functions of a BMS are based on data input from and data output to various interfaces. Voltage, current, and temperature are retrieved from sensors that are connected to the BMS, e.g., via serial peripheral interface (SPI), controller area network (CAN), local interconnect network (LIN), or bluetooth low energy (BLE). WiFi or BLE can also connect slave and master modules in a wireless architecture design [25]. The connections to other ECUs, e.g., to the IVI for displaying current battery data or to the VCU for receiving control information for the battery, are mainly established via CAN or (automotive) Ethernet. The BMS does not have a direct cloud connection. Usually, the BMS is connected to a gateway via CAN or Ethernet that establishes a connection to a cloud via a cellular network. There is also a mediating device between the BMS and the

electric vehicle supply equipment (EVSE), i.e., the charging station: The electric vehicle charging controller (EVCC), also referred to as on-board charger (OBC) manages the communication between the charging station and the vehicle. The connection is mainly achieved via Ethernet.

3 RELATED WORK

3.1 BMS System Environment

The literature already mentioned in the previous section ([1, 16–19, 25, 29]) also describes system environments of BMS, e.g., in EVs. For example, Kim et al. [16] present an architecture for a cyber-physical BMS consisting of, on the one hand, a wirelessly connected module management system with an internet of things (IoT) device for data collection and communication with internal and external parties and, on the other hand, a cloud battery management platform with a database, analysis tools, algorithms and visualization. And according to Krishna et al. [17], connections are established to the grid, graphical interfaces, and networks in general. It can be summarized that components like EVCC, gateway, cloud, and other ECUs of the vehicle built the system environment inside an EV, which are elaborated later in Section 4. Since the BMS is currently replaced when the battery is used in a second life application, it seems reasonable for the mentioned authors to describe only one singular system environment. However, the new EU regulation on batteries and waste batteries mandates to enable BMS with functionalities to install non-OEM battery management software for second life use [7]. Current literature lacks a continued description of the system environment, including a second life.

3.2 BMS life cycle

Generally, the overarching life cycle phases in the first and second life cycle scenarios can be considered conceptually equivalent. To the best of our knowledge, research works dedicated to only the life cycle of a BMS do not exist. Significantly, research on the security aspects across the entire life cycle still needs to be included. Since the BMS is logically inseparable from a battery, we utilize literature describing the life cycle of a battery [4, 8, 21, 31]. The authors generally describe the same or similar life cycle stages of a battery. For example, Gohla-Neudecker et al. [8] define battery manufacturing, the first life of the battery in an EV, battery return and assessment, re-purposing, integration of the new battery system, the second life in, e.g., a smart grid, and finally the battery EOL recycling. Zhu et al. [31] detail the transitioning steps: incoming assessment, evaluation of battery performance, sorting and regrouping of cells or packs, and development of control strategies for second life applications.

The analogy to the life of an IoT device, as introduced in [23] and [30], can also be taken into account to structure this identification process. According to Rahman et al. [23], construction, production, installation and commissioning, operation, update, and decommissioning are typical life cycle stages of IoT devices. Yousefnezhad et al. [30] adds the additional phase of re-ownership.

Summarizing the previous research activities in this field, a complete life cycle of a BMS consists of the first life stages: production, integration, shipping/delivery, operation, and end of first life, and of the similar second life stages: production, integration, shipping/installation, operation, and end of second life (Figure 2).

3.3 Problem Description

The current literature describes activities across the life cycle, especially during the transition, mostly on a battery cell level. Individual security controls exist for first and second life applications but are not described as continuing security measures. Additionally, the life cycles of IoT devices can be compared to those of BMS only to a limited account since the general system environment does not change in case of a re-ownership of IoT devices.

Therefore, no active research currently addresses the transition from the first to the second life phase, particularly regarding the individual cybersecurity threats relevant to this transition. Nevertheless, it can be assumed that even without the aforementioned EU requirement [7], BMSs will be reused for the second life phase in certain future use cases and scenarios.

This paper aims to provide needs on security controls during this transition phase, filling the missing items shown in Figure 2. We, therefore, define the system environment of the first and second life. Since the battery cells usually remain the same, looking closely at the changing environment is essential. On this basis, the security-relevant activities are analyzed over the entire life cycle. Based on the system environment and the life cycle activities, the transition phase between the two lives can be defined, and needs for security mechanisms can be given. Our analysis follows a use-case-based approach, where we assume that the first life takes place in a vehicle and the second life in an energy storage system (ESS), taking into account their individual system environment and security activities.

4 ANALYSIS OF BMS SYSTEM ENVIRONMENT

We define the system environment as the surrounding devices and communication partners outside the BMS. While the BMS and associated cells remain the same from the first life to the second and other lives as defined earlier, the system environment changes: during the first life, the BMS interacts mainly with internal vehicle-, charging-, and cloud-systems. The communication partners and associated tasks differ depending on the usage scenario in the subsequent lives. Figure 3 gives an overview of the system environment of first and second life.

4.1 First Life

The hardware-related environment of the BMS in its first life is mainly defined by surrounding vehicle parts and comprises other ECUs of the vehicle like the VCU or the IVI, gateway module(s), the on-board charger (EVCC), and the charging station (EVSE). Regarding software parts, they are embedded into the vehicle software environment, linked with other components, and connected to cloud services.

4.1.1 ECUs, Vehicle Components. Unique for the BMS operation in a vehicle is the connection and thus the communication with other ECUs. The BMS exchanges data on the current SoC and SoE with the VCU, which uses the data to compute the possible and optimal energy delivery. Data will also be exchanged with the IVI to transfer the SoC and SoH. The latter will be mandatory to fulfill new regulations [7]. Data demanding the charging of a certain amount of energy is an example of communication between the IVI and the BMS or the EVCC. Future applications may also communicate

Figure 2: Exemplary life cycle phases of battery with first and second life.

Figure 3: BMS model and surrounding system environment for first, second, and optional third life. Only the BMS and battery are taken over into a second life. The connections between the components represent logical links.

weather and street conditions information detected by other ECUs to the BMS to optimize the battery [5].

4.1.2 *EVCC, EVSE.* To enable charging of the battery, the EVCC communicates with a charging station (EVSE). Specific to automotive BMS is the non-static connection to the EVSE: as it is possible to charge the vehicle at any public or private charging station, the technology must be able to adapt dynamically to the different technologies and communication protocols implemented by the various EVSEs. Although there are standards, the spectrum of technologies is still broad. The range of possible protocols will continue to increase as communication between the vehicle and charging station will be established wirelessly [6].

4.1.3 *Gateway, Cloud.* The BMS itself does not usually communicate directly with a server in the cloud, although this may be possible depending on the architecture of the vehicle’s electrical system. Instead, a gateway is used as a mediating device: the BMS communicates with the gateway, and the gateway establishes a connection to the cloud and transfers the data. Depending on the location and use case, this is established via cellular or WiFi. Different (backend) servers are involved on the cloud side: data storage of the Battery Pass, repository for software updates, or cloud services provided by the OEM allowing, e.g., remote maintenance.

4.2 Second Life

The system environment of the second life heavily depends on the usage scenario. For example, in their patent, Hall and Stern [9] define an energy storage system comprising multiple battery packs managed by a supervising BMS. Other applications use only (slave-)modules of the original battery pack. So, the BMS’s range of functions and interfaces can differ from those in its first life.

4.2.1 *ESS-BMS.* We define the ESS-BMS as the intermediate system between the energy source, e.g., the grid or energy stations driven by hydroelectric or PV, the consuming devices, and the first life BMS. This device supervises multiple battery packs or modules as a master. Therefore, connections must be established between the BMS and the ESS-BMS. In its first life, this function was fulfilled by the VCU and the EVCC. The interface technologies and protocols likely differ between first and second life.

4.2.2 *Gateway, Cloud.* The connection to the cloud will be technologically equal to the first life. Depending on the architecture, the BMS or the ESS-BMS will establish a remote connection via a gateway. Since each of the first life battery packs has a unique Battery Pass to be continued in the second life, an interface to the corresponding servers must be provided. The battery system is no longer maintained by the first life automotive OEM, so backend servers like software update repositories, maintenance consoles, or

emergency services will be different than in the first life. However, changing server connections is not only limited to the second life but can also occur during the first life.

5 ANALYSIS OF BMS CYBERSECURITY LIFE CYCLE

The following sections describe battery-related and cybersecurity-related activities during the different life cycle stages. The applicable phases follow the structure that as been already defined in Figure 2. Due to the individual characteristics of a battery pack and the wide range of different second life applications, the described life cycle is only a blueprint for some battery types and applications. However, the activities mentioned in each phase are a likely life cycle and align with related approaches as described in Section 3. Table 1 summarizes the phases and their corresponding battery-related and cybersecurity-related activities. The production of the BMS and the battery cells marks the first stage of the life cycle defined within this paper. We do not mention the software development life cycle separately. However, common automotive standards such as ISO 26262 [13] for safety or ISO/SAE 21434 [15] for security software applications are applicable.

The sections first describe the general activities carried out in this phase and then place them in the context of the relevant security considerations. We mark each security control or security-relevant activity with an identifier. If the control has already been mentioned, the identifier is omitted. First life security controls are marked with **A_x** and those of the second life with **B_x**. To define the transition, the identifier will be used in Section 6.

5.1 First Life

The first life of the BMS starts with the production of the battery and ends when its capacity degrades so that it cannot be used in an EV anymore and has to be removed from the vehicle. In the following paragraphs, the operational activities of the BMS and the activities related to cybersecurity in these different phases are explained in more detail.

5.1.1 Production.

Description of the phase. The production of the battery comprises the fabrication of cells, modules, and packs, as well as the initial production and assembly of the BMS printed circuit board (PCB). The BMS is usually a commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) component produced by a tier supplier. The cells and the BMS are bound together and build one unit.

Security considerations. A unique and secure identity (**A1**) has to be generated to distinguish single units from each other. We define a unit as a module or a pack. The ID is also needed for the Battery Pass (**A2**), created and initialized in this phase. Cryptographic keys (**A3**) must be created and derived initially. Certificates (**A4**) as a document for binding identities and cryptographic keys must be installed to be prepared for the communication activities of the subsequent phases of life. The BMS firmware (**A5**) is also installed in this phase to enable monitoring and control of the battery. Preparing the BMS bootloader to enable secure software updates (**A6**), e.g., by integrating secure boot, is an essential step in this phase and relies on creating cryptographic keys previously. In the production

phase, the battery pack is physically built. Therefore, perimeter protections (**A7**) against attackers have to be integrated during this phase.

5.1.2 Integration.

Description of the phase. We define the integration phase as building the electric vehicle and integrating the battery. The interfaces between the vehicle and the battery are connected physically.

Security considerations. As the vehicle is ready to ship after this phase, on-boarding into a vehicle security operations center (VSOC) (**A8**) and a cybersecurity management system (CSMS) (**A9**) as required in the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) norm R155 [26] as well as establishing connection to OEM backend servers (**A10**) must be done at this stage. A security configuration (**A11**) applicable to the specific vehicle is loaded. With integrating the battery into the vehicle, an update of the Battery Pass connecting the vehicle's identity is also applicable. The final assembly finishes with end of line (EOL) tests, including the first in-vehicle battery charging.

5.1.3 Shipping/Delivery.

Description of the phase. The transition from the OEM to the car owner is described in the stage *shipping/delivery*. The transport of EVs introduces safety risks due to the high-voltage battery.

Security considerations. Vehicles are set into a special mode for transportation (**A12**) in which the functional extent is limited to a minimum [2]. It must be ensured that the vehicle, especially the BMS, is also protected in this phase, which applies to safety and security. Updates, including the latest firmware and customer-specific features (**A13**), are applied in this phase. Since this will alter the functional scope, the BMS' attack surface will likely increase. Once delivered, the vehicle is expected to be integrated into private and public networks (**A14**), further enlarging the attack surface for the BMS.

5.1.4 Operation.

Description of the phase. The transition between the delivery of the vehicle to the owner and the vehicle's operation happens smoothly and cannot be strictly bounded. The BMS must be in operation mode after integrating it into the vehicle, as the battery must be monitored and controlled from then on. However, since the operation stage is the primary and longest phase of the battery's first life, activities that also apply to other phases are mentioned here. These are monitoring and controlling the battery parameters and calculating statuses like SoC or SoH. Communicating with other ECUs or parties outside the vehicle is mandatory for crucial functions like charging and provisioning of energy. It also enables additional secondary functions like remote monitoring, VSOC integration, functions standardized in ISO15118 [14] (Plug'n'Charge, V2G), or the Battery Pass.

Security considerations. Manipulated or missing sensor values can result in incorrect monitoring and status calculation, which seriously ensures the occupants' safety and the vehicle's performance. Therefore, protecting the data acquisition (**A15**), e.g., against false-data-injections, is essential. Ensuring confidentiality, integrity,

Table 1: BMS Cybersecurity Life Cycle

Stage	Activities	Cybersecurity-Activities
First Life		
Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Battery assembly •BMS construction •Integration of BMS & battery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Identity creation •Key generation •Installing physical protection •Software flashing •Battery Pass creation
Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Integration of battery and vehicle •Interface connection •End-of-Line tests •In-Vehicle battery charging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Security configuration loading •VSOC on-boarding •CSMS integration •OEM server connection •Battery Pass update
Shipping/Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Transport mode •Customer handover 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Customer-specific features activation •SW-Updates •Integration of private/public networks
Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Monitoring & control •Status calculation •Internal & external communication •Ownership transfer •Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Protection of data acquisition •Communication security •Access control •SW-Updates •Certificate management •Charging communication •Data upload •Security configuration
End of first life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Battery removal from vehicle •Battery transportation •Battery state assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Removal of OEM SW/configuration •VSOC off-boarding •Access control •Data manipulation verification •Battery Pass update
Second Life		
Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Production of second life system •Battery adaptation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Updating physical protection
Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •New interfaces •New architecture •New communication parties •Integration of battery and second life system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •SW-Updates •Security configuration •Certificate management •Key management •Battery Pass update
Shipping/Installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Transport mode •Connection to customer environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •SOC on-boarding •SW-Updates
Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Monitoring & control •Status calculation •Internal and external communication •Reduced tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Protection of data acquisition •Communication security •Access control •SW-Updates •Certificate management •Charging communication •Data upload •Security configuration •Advanced physical protection
End of second life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Battery removal •Battery state assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Battery Pass update •Removal of OEM SW/configuration •SOC off-boarding

availability, authenticity, and non-repudiation of communication (**A16**) between the BMS and its corresponding partners is a mandatory security activity during the operation phase. Communication protection is accompanied by executing access control (**A17**) functionalities, which is also relevant when it comes to maintenance activities: workshops will have different rights to communicate with the battery than the owner. As mentioned in other phases, software updates must be executed securely. Updates are not only used to add additional functions but also to fix security vulnerabilities. Vulnerability management has to be processed by the OEM, which is also required in the UNECE norm R156 [27]. Certificate management (**A18**) (certificate update, certificate revocation) and the update of security configurations (key update, roles) are also tasks that apply throughout the phase of operation. Both are also relevant when the vehicle's owner changes: user-specific certificates must be revoked, and new certificates must be installed. The Battery Pass requires a periodic upload of battery-related data. The existence of authentic data is an essential prerequisite for correct implementation and unaltered meaningfulness of the Battery Pass [3].

5.1.5 Decommissioning.

Description of the phase. The end of the first life is reached if the battery's capacity is degraded to 80% of its original capacity, which is a definition of the EOL set by the United States Advanced Battery Consortium (USABC) [28]. The battery is removed from the vehicle and prepared for transportation. The battery's SoH is assessed to find the best-fitting second life application.

Security considerations. Considered security activities include the removal or transfer of OEM software, security configurations, and intellectual property (IP) (**A19**), e.g., the OEM root certificates or OEM specific software parts. As the battery is no longer a vehicle component, the off-boarding process from the VSOC (**A20**) must be carried out. The Battery Pass has to be updated as well to document the decommissioning. Since the status of the battery is assessed between both lives, it has to be verified that the battery data has not been tampered with. Status manipulation could maliciously falsify the resale value. Finally, the battery is prepared for transportation, ensuring a safe transfer. Since the interfaces are more easily accessible during transportation and can be used as a potential attack vector, a particular focus has to be placed on enforcing access control rules.

5.2 Second Life

The second life generally contains the same phases as the first life. However, since the system environment is different (see Section 4), changes in tasks, communication activities, and processes arise thus altering cybersecurity activities.

5.2.1 Production.

Description of the phase. We define the production of the second life system as the manufacturing of the components surrounding the battery, e.g., a housing, supervisory thermal management system, or control mechanisms, and the adaptation of the battery to the new system. New interfaces, e.g., to thermal management systems or other new components, thus requiring new software, can be applied.

Security considerations. There are only a few security-relevant activities. We assume the battery system is not subject to significant changes, so the security controls mainly relate to the surrounding components. However, an adaptation of the perimeter protection (**B1**) mechanisms must be integrated, as the battery may be more easily accessible.

5.2.2 Integration.

Description of the phase. Integrating the battery and the second life system follows the production phase. Interfaces between the battery and other system components must be connected to support the new system architecture. In this phase, the second life ESS will be set up to be fully functional.

Security considerations. During the integration phase, either updated software (**B2**) is deployed or a new firmware is installed (**B3**), new cryptographic keys (**B4**) are generated, and existing certificates are updated (**B5**), or new certificates (**B6**) are installed. The second life system introduces new parties with whom the BMS must communicate (see Section 4.2), e.g., backend servers (**B7**) of the new OEM or private household networks (**B8**). Therefore, an updated security configuration (**B9**) applies. The integration of the battery into the new system environment has to be documented in the Battery Pass (**B10**).

5.2.3 Shipping/Installation.

Description of the phase. The *shipping* phase may not be relevant for every second life application. Since the second life system is usually operated at a stationary location, the integration phase can already occur at the place of use, making shipping obsolete.

Security considerations. However, in case of required shipping, a transport mode (**B11**) for the battery has to be activated to ensure a safe transfer, which also includes a particular view on enforcing rules for access control (**B12**) to prevent manipulations. Regardless of the transfer, installation steps must be carried out. The integration of the second life system and thus of the BMS as one component has to be integrated into a customer's security operations center (SOC) (**B13**) if available. A SOC monitors the system for suspicious activities and can activate countermeasures to protect the system and the company's infrastructure.

5.2.4 Operation.

Description of the phase. The general functionalities of the BMS remain the same: monitoring and control of the battery, status calculation, and communication with internal and external partners. Depending on the second life application, the BMS can be only a sub-component of a compound of several battery packs. Therefore, there may be a higher-level ESS-BMS which monitors, controls, and calculates the statuses of the whole system and takes over higher-level tasks like thermal management, thus resulting in a reduced amount of tasks for a single BMS.

Security considerations. The security considerations are similar to those of the first life. The steps of data acquisition (**B14**) have to be protected. The communication with other parties (**B15**), internal and external, has to be secured. Software updates apply. Certificate management has to be processed continuously to update, revoke,

and install certificates. The second life system is usually stationary, which can introduce easier accessibility and increase the attack surface. Therefore, perimeter protection mechanisms must be more advanced than in the first life, and software-based access mechanisms must be more tightly controlled. Regarding the Battery Pass, battery-related data has to be uploaded as well. The second life system can consist of several battery packs or modules, all of which already have a Battery Pass, which requires extended identity management (B16).

5.2.5 Decommissioning/Disposal.

Description of the phase. The end of the second life is reached if the battery cells are no longer usable, even for the second life. In this phase, the battery is removed from the system, and an intensive assessment of the battery's state has to be executed. As a result, the battery may be either dismantled and the cell materials recycled, or the battery may still be usable for other applications. This paper does not describe recycling processes or use in applications beyond second life. However, the latter does not significantly differ from the processes and mechanisms of second life.

Security considerations. All IP of the OEM or personal data of the owner stored inside the BMS must be securely removed (B17) at this stage, which also applies to the off-boarding from the SOC (B18). Finally, the process of decommissioning or disposal has to be documented in the Battery Pass. In case of an EOL of the battery, the Battery Pass can be deleted or archived afterward. It must be ensured that the Battery Pass and its unique identity cannot be reused (B19), e.g., to provide identities for counterfeit batteries.

6 TRANSITION AND CYBERSECURITY NEEDS

In the last two chapters, we identified the system environment of first and second life applications and the security measures throughout the life cycle of the battery and its corresponding BMS. With this information, we can define the transition phase between the two phases of life and describe activities regarding cybersecurity that should be considered during this phase. This allows us to fill the gap between first and second life shown in Figure 2.

6.1 Definition of the Transition Phase

The transition phase is described as every action that must occur between the battery's system state in the first life and the battery's system state in the second life. From a cybersecurity perspective, this includes all activities that need to be performed to seamlessly transform any security control that takes place in both the first and second lives. It also includes the security controls, which must be active between the two lives. Activities can comprise updates, replacements, or transfer processes from a procedural point of view.

The results of comparing the security controls and defining transitions can be found in Table 2: the table compares the first and second life security controls as analyzed and emphasizes corresponding transition activities. If the security control exists in the first or second life, it is marked with a ✓. Also, the applicable transition activities are marked with a ✓. The transition action *No* means that the security control is the same in the first and second life. The transition action *Update* means that the security control should stay in the system but requires an update to facilitate the new system

environment requirements. The transition action *Replace* means that the security control of the first life is entirely removed and replaced by a newly developed control.

No transition is necessary for those that exist only in one life. However, particularly in the case of security elements only present in second life applications, it must be checked whether the first life BMS must already be prepared for them. We see this as part of our future work.

Security controls or items that do not need an active transitioning are the battery pack's identity, the corresponding Battery Pass, the BMS firmware, the battery's transportation mode, protection of the data acquisition, methods for deletion of IP, and processes of off-boarding it from VSOC and SOC. However, all of these mechanisms require a transition of documentation to enable the new operator to use them properly. For example, the credentials to the Battery Pass and methods to read out the identity need to be transferred. Other security controls require to be updated. Update means, in this context, that the general implementation of the security control remains the same as it was implemented in the first life. However, a modification of, e.g., configuration items or interfaces is necessary. Controls covered by this transition activity include the BMS firmware, methods for secure software updates, including enabling secure boot, perimeter protection, secure communication with external parties, access control rules, and updating certificates. Finally, there are security controls that have to be entirely replaced, which include cryptographic keys, the creation of new certificates, the BMS firmware, integration into a SOC, connections to backend servers, and private or public networks.

The BMS firmware is mentioned in each possible transition activity and is, therefore, a particular case: it heavily depends on the second life application if the BMS firmware can be used *as it is*, requires an update, or has to be entirely replaced. However, the actual second life application is likely not defined at the beginning of life, making it challenging to set only on transition activity.

6.2 Cybersecurity Needs

Summarizing the analysis above, we formulate the following needs to transfer the BMS security measures from a first to a second life. The list is not in any particular order.

- a. User data should be securely deleted to prevent any conclusions from being drawn about the previous user.
- b. Secure deletion of OEM-specific cryptographic material, such as root certificates and authentication data for backend servers, should be guaranteed.
- c. Mechanisms for detecting manipulated software should also be installed in second life applications. Therefore, transitioning from one OEM to another must be facilitated.
- d. Responsibility for the Battery Pass, including credentials for various roles, should be transferred when transitioning between OEMs.
- e. Mechanisms for reading and modifying the identity of a battery should be transferred.
- f. Obsolete access rules should be removed while ensuring accessibility for the device's second life OEM and associated rules.

Table 2: Comparison of First and Second Life Security Controls and Corresponding Transition Activity

	Security Item	First Life	Second Life	Transition		
				No	Update	Replace
A1/B16	Identity	✓	✓	✓		
A2/B10	Battery Pass	✓	✓	✓		
A3/B4	Cryptographic Keys	✓	✓			✓
A4/B6	Certificates creation	✓	✓		✓	✓
A5/B3	BMS firmware	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
A6/B2	Secure software updates	✓	✓		✓	
A7/B1	Perimeter protection	✓	✓		✓	
A8/B13	VSOC/SOC	✓	✓			✓
A9	CSMS	✓				
A10/B7	Backend server	✓	✓			✓
A11/B9	Security configuration	✓	✓		✓	
A12/B11	Transportation mode	✓	✓	✓		
A13	Customer-specific functions	✓				
A14/B8	Private/public networks	✓	✓			✓
A15/B14	Data acquisition protection	✓	✓	✓		
A16/B15	Secure communication	✓	✓		✓	
A17/B12	Access control	✓	✓		✓	
A18/B5	Certificate management	✓	✓		✓	
A19/B17	IP deletion	✓	✓	✓		
A20/B18	VSOC/SOC off-boarding	✓	✓	✓		
B19	Battery Pass deletion		✓			

- g. Perimeter protection mechanisms should be enforced during transfer, allowing the second life OEM to open and remove them.
- h. Connections and credentials associated with external networks, whether public or private, should be deleted.
- i. The integration in VSOC and CSMS should be terminated. Data can be exchanged if relevant.

6.3 Discussion

The practicability of the identified cybersecurity needs is highlighted through three application examples. To capture a wide range of possible scenarios, we have selected one example that focuses on large ESSs in the corporate or government sector and another that looks at smaller private energy storage solutions. We also explore the logistical challenges associated with second life applications, regardless of the type of application.

Companies such as Connected Energy Ltd.¹ and B2U Storage Solutions Inc.² are building large ESSs with a potential energy storage capacity of up to several megawatts. They incorporate second life

battery packs from automotive OEMs like Renault, Nissan, or Tesla in their ESS. Each battery pack is used as it was installed in the EV, so neither cells nor modules need to be dismantled. When incorporating such battery packs in a new ESS, the communication channels to the first life OEM and so the OEM-specific cryptographic material (root certificates, authentication data, etc.) have to be withdrawn since there is no need to communicate with those backend systems during second life. There may be an opportunity to share key material between both OEMs. However, this poses additional security risks, as the attack surface on the transmission and storage of keys is considerably increased. The disclosure of the first life OEM's cryptographic material can also threaten its entire fleet of vehicles. Secure deletion and reinstallation of these keys is, therefore, a considered solution as long as the key storage component is able to also generate new cryptographic material. Other second life battery ESS are built for private households and are used, e.g., to store energy generated by photovoltaic systems. These systems are operated in an open environment not controlled by the OEM. Therefore, the new owner may get access to the system, e.g., to integrate it into smart home applications, thus being able to read data stored in the BMS. To ensure that no conclusions can be drawn about the previous user of the battery, user data should be

¹<https://connected-energy.co.uk/>, last accessed 11.06.2024

²<https://www.b2uco.com/>, last accessed 11.06.2024

securely deleted before it is delivered to the customer. Other data, such as credentials, e.g., for the Battery Pass, must be transferred to the new owner as the product passport obligation does not only apply to batteries installed in EVs.

Both applications are subject to the same considerations regarding the physical transition and transportation from the first life to their second application. It must be ensured that no party can maliciously manipulate the BMS and thus seriously jeopardize the safety of the battery. Manipulation detection is already needed during the first life to ensure a correct calculation of the SoH, remaining useful life, and correct data input into the Battery Pass. The mechanisms are also important in second life. Forensic detection of manipulations usually depends on historical logging data. To continuously ensure manipulation detection, these mechanisms and their corresponding data must be transferred to a second life OEM. Sharing functions and data across different OEMs introduces the non-technical challenge of protecting their IP, i.e., firmware, configuration data, and documentation of interfaces, wiring, and software functions. It also has to be decided who is legally responsible for these common items.

7 CONCLUSION

Batteries from EVs are suitable for reuse in a second life once they can no longer be used to power vehicles. Securing the BMS throughout the entire life is a mandatory requirement to ensure cybersecurity goals at every stage. We showed the research gap in the transition phase between first and second life applications. This gap is why, in many real-world scenarios, the whole BMS is replaced during the transition, wasting resources. To address this gap, our analysis named the necessary cybersecurity activities and concerns to allow for the secure reuse of a BMS for second life applications. As discussed in Section 6.3, the cybersecurity requirements are also practically applicable and feasible, which we have illustrated using three example applications. However, we also explored additional challenges that these needs entail and need to be solved. Multiple questions must be evaluated, and mitigation strategies for cybersecurity needs must be identified. These questions are not only technical but also of a legal and contractual nature and must be resolved individually by the OEMs or the regulatory authority. The results of this comprehensive investigation can serve as a starting point for initiating a TARA based on the automotive security standard ISO/SAE 21434. Future activities will also analyze existing methods and processes to transfer security controls into second life applications seamlessly and investigate BMS designs allowing a secure first and second life.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Muhammad Umair Ali, Amad Zafar, Sarvar Hussain Nengroo, Sadam Hussain, Muhammad Junaid Alvi, and Hee-Je Kim. 2019. Towards a Smarter Battery Management System for Electric Vehicle Applications: A Critical Review of Lithium-Ion Battery State of Charge Estimation. *Energies* 12, 3 (2019), 446. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12030446>
- [2] AUTOSAR. 2022. Requirements on Mode Management AUTOSAR CP R22-11.
- [3] Julian Blümke and Hans-Joachim Hof. 2023. Binding the Battery to the Pass: An Approach to Trustworthy Product Life Cycle Data by Using Certificates Based on PUFs. *International Journal on Advances in Security* vol. 16, no 1 & 2 (2023), 44–53.
- [4] Martin F. Börner, Moritz H. Frieges, Benedikt Späth, Kathrin Spütz, Heiner H. Heimes, Dirk Uwe Sauer, and Weihai Li. 2022. Challenges of second-life concepts for retired electric vehicle batteries. *Cell Reports Physical Science* 3, 10 (2022), 101095. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2022.101095>
- [5] Sajib Chakraborty, Mohamed El Baghdadi, Joris Jaguemont, Cedric de Cauwer, Bicheng Chen, Alexander Wahl, Patrick Manns, Caroline Ngo, Antonio Sciarretta, and Omar Hegazy. 2021. Parameterized Cloud-Connected Electro-Thermal Modelling of a Battery Electric Vehicle. In *2021 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*. IEEE, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/VPPC53923.2021.9699175>
- [6] Sidina El Jeilani, Hassan El Fadil, Abdellah Lassioui, Tasnime Bouanou, Oumaima Benzouina, Halima Housny, and Mostapha Oulcaïd. 2024. Wireless Communication Systems Applied to Ev Wireless Charger: State of the Art. In *Automatic Control and Emerging Technologies*, Hassan El Fadil and Weicun Zhang (Eds.). Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, Vol. 1141. Springer Nature Singapore, Singapore, 41–49. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-0126-1_4
- [7] European Parliament, Council of the European Union. 2023. Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC. *Official Journal of the European Union* 66 (2023). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1542/oj>
- [8] B. Gohla-Neudecker, M. Bowler, and S. Mohr. 2015. Battery 2nd/>sup>life: Leveraging the sustainability potential of EVs and renewable energy grid integration. In *2015 International Conference on Clean Electrical Power (ICCEP)*. IEEE, 311–318. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCEP.2015.7177641>
- [9] Freeman Stoflet Hall and Michael Joseph Stern. 2022. US 11,289,921 B1: Energy-Storage System Employing Second-Life Electric Vehicle Batteries. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11289921B1/en>
- [10] Andreas Herzig, Philip Roth, and Ritika Kochar. 2023. *The Car As A Digital Platform: On-Demand Car Features*. Whitepaper. Deloitte GmbH. <https://www2.deloitte.com/de/de/pages/risk/articles/on-demand-car-features.html>
- [11] IEA. 2023. Global EV Outlook 2023. <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-ev-outlook-2023>
- [12] Infineon Technologies AG. 2022. Understanding and overcoming the challenges of building high voltage automotive battery management systems.
- [13] ISO. 2018. Road vehicles – Functional safety.
- [14] ISO. 2019. ISO 15118-1:2019 Road vehicles – Vehicle to grid communication interface – Part 1: General information and use-case definition.
- [15] ISO. 2021. ISO/SAE 21434:2021 - Road vehicles - Cybersecurity engineering.
- [16] Taesik Kim, Darshan Makwana, Amit Adhikaree, Jitendra Vagdoda, and Young Lee. 2018. Cloud-Based Battery Condition Monitoring and Fault Diagnosis Platform for Large-Scale Lithium-Ion Battery Energy Storage Systems. *Energies* 11, 1 (2018), 125. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11010125>
- [17] Gopal Krishna, Rajesh Singh, Anita Gehlot, Shaik Vaseem Akram, Neeraj Priyadarshi, and Bhekisipho Twala. 2022. Digital Technology Implementation in Battery-Management Systems for Sustainable Energy Storage: Review, Challenges, and Recommendations. *Electronics* 11, 17 (2022), 2695. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11172695>
- [18] Panpan Liu, Changbo Lu, Changfu Wang, Xudong Wang, Wanli Xu, Youjie Zhou, and Hua Li. 2021. Research Status and Development of Battery Management System. In *Communications, Signal Processing, and Systems*, Qilian Liang, Wei Wang, Xin Liu, Zhenyu Na, Xiaoxia Li, and Baoju Zhang (Eds.). Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, Vol. 654. Springer Singapore, Singapore, 1422–1429. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-8411-4_189
- [19] Farshid Naseri, Zahra Kazemi, Peter Gorm Larsen, Mohammad Mehdi Arefi, and Erik Schaltz. 2023. Cyber-Physical Cloud Battery Management Systems: Review of Security Aspects. *Batteries* 9, 7 (2023), 382. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries9070382>
- [20] NXP Semiconductors. 2022. NXP high-voltage battery management system reference design helps developers get ahead of the curve.
- [21] Linda Olsson, Sara Fallahi, Maria Schnurr, Derek Diener, and Patricia van Loon. 2018. Circular Business Models for Extended EV Battery Life. *Batteries* 4, 4 (2018), 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries4040057>
- [22] Nitika G. Panwar, Surinder Singh, Akhil Garg, Abhishek Kumar Gupta, and Liang Gao. 2021. Recent Advancements in Battery Management System for Li-Ion Batteries of Electric Vehicles: Future Role of Digital Twin, Cyber-Physical Systems, Battery Swapping Technology, and Nondestructive Testing. *Energy Technology* 9, 8 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202000984>
- [23] Leila Fatmasari Rahman, Tanir Ozcelebi, and Johan Lukkien. 2018. Understanding IoT Systems: A Life Cycle Approach. *Procedia Computer Science* 130 (2018), 1057–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.04.148>
- [24] Carlos António Rufino Júnior, Eleonora Riva Sanserverino, Pierluigi Gallo, Daniel Koch, Yash Kotak, Hans-Georg Schweiger, and Hudson Zanin. 2023. Towards a business model for second-life batteries: Barriers, opportunities, uncertainties,

- and technologies. *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 78 (2023), 507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2022.12.019>
- [25] Akash Samanta and Sheldon S. Williamson. 2021. A Survey of Wireless Battery Management System: Topology, Emerging Trends, and Challenges. *Electronics* 10, 18 (2021), 2193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics10182193>
- [26] UNECE R155 2021. UN Regulation No 155 – Uniform provisions concerning the approval of vehicles with regards to cybersecurity and cybersecurity management system [2021/387].
- [27] UNECE R156 2021. UN Regulation No 156 – Uniform provisions concerning the approval of vehicles with regards to software update and software updates management system [2021/388].
- [28] United States Advanced Battery Consortium. 1996. Electric Vehicle Battery Test Procedures Manual, Revision 2.
- [29] Huaibin Wang, Shuyu Wang, Xuning Feng, Xuan Zhang, Kangwei Dai, Jun Sheng, Zhenyang Zhao, Zhiming Du, Zelin Zhang, Kai Shen, Chengshan Xu, Qinzhen Wang, Xiaoyu Sun, Yanliang Li, Jiaju Ling, Jiani Feng, Hewu Wang, and Minggao Ouyang. 2021. An experimental study on the thermal characteristics of the Cell-To-Pack system. *Energy* 227 (2021), 120338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120338>
- [30] Narges Yousefnezhad, Avleen Malhi, and Kary Främling. 2020. Security in product lifecycle of IoT devices: A survey. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications* 171 (2020), 102779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2020.102779>
- [31] Juner Zhu, Ian Mathews, Dongsheng Ren, Wei Li, Daniel Cogswell, Bobin Xing, Tobias Sedlatschek, Sai Nithin R. Kantareddy, Mengchao Yi, Tao Gao, Yong Xia, Qing Zhou, Tomasz Wierzbicki, and Martin Z. Bazant. 2021. End-of-life or second-life options for retired electric vehicle batteries. *Cell Reports Physical Science* 2, 8 (2021), 100537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2021.100537>